

Empowering Teachers to Identify Quality Game Based Learning Solutions

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Abstract—There has been a significant increase in the development and usage of educational technology applications, with game-based learning solutions being one major category. Game based learning solutions have been known to provide stimulating and dynamic environments that give learners engaging and interactive experiences. They can have different learning objectives and contain a diverse set of features. At the same time, teachers may wish to use game-based learning solutions in their classes in different contexts such as topics and learner age groups. Such a diversity in game-based learning solutions and the varied needs makes it challenging for a teacher to decide a suitable game-based learning solution for her context. While various evaluation frameworks and guidelines exist, they typically address the requirements of researchers or designers of game-based learning solutions. Certain checklists also exist for generic educational technology applications. In our previous work, we found a lack of solutions for teachers in the Indian context who need easily usable evaluation frameworks that can help them select quality game-based learning applications for their students in their classes. In this paper, we present our efforts under the EdTech Tulna project to address this need. We report the design of a research based index (Tulna GBL index) to evaluate the quality of maths game-based learning solutions, followed by the details of a training session for teachers to use the index. We conducted a study to analyze teachers’ perceptions regarding the usability and usefulness of the Tulna GBL index. Our findings show that the Tulna GBL index can be a practical and easy-to-use tool for teachers addressing their goals of selecting effective learning solutions.

Keywords— *Game-based learning, EdTech evaluation frameworks, Teacher use of educational games*

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the usage of games in educational settings has become more widespread. Educational games and game-based learning (GBL) solutions have shown to have positive impacts on students’ motivation, engagement, information retention, and overall academic achievement [1]. Numerous GBL solutions are available for different subjects in various languages of instruction targeting different age groups. While there exist global standards and frameworks for evaluating the quality of educational technology (EdTech) solutions, their adoption is hindered due to the contextual nature of teaching and learning [2]. Researchers have created and validated evaluation frameworks and instruments [3][4], but are they often generic across different types of EdTech products. Quality frameworks specific to GBL solutions mostly cater to researchers and designers.

The National Education Policy (2020) [5] by the Indian government encourages the use of affordances of technology in schools. Hence there is a requirement to sensitize teachers and school officials about good quality EdTech solutions to aid in informed decision-making. In this paper, we present our efforts to support teachers to make systematic decisions

on selecting quality GBL solutions for their context. This work is part of the broader EdTech Tulna project [6]. We designed a research-backed context-specific evaluation index which we will refer to as the Tulna GBL index. We also conducted a training session to sensitize teachers in identifying quality EdTech GBL solutions for teaching mathematics using the Tulna GBL index. Participants included 45 teachers spanning grades 6-10. The training session provided insight into specific challenges that teachers face while choosing and using GBL solutions. As part of the session, we conducted a study to understand teachers’ perceptions regarding the challenges they face while choosing and using GBL solutions, and to analyze the usability and usefulness of the Tulna GBL index.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW: EVALUATING QUALITY OF GAME-BASED LEARNING SOLUTIONS

Numerous frameworks addressing different aspects of GBL solutions have been created. Some frameworks provide design principles and recommendations for the key considerations needed for the design of GBL such as game motivators or give pedagogical considerations [7-12]. Others are evaluation instruments and checklists [8][9]. Some evaluate the pedagogical and technological design of the solution while others evaluate the learning outcomes, learning interaction, learning experience, etc. [10]. Also available are studies that provide empirical evidence for the value of games and simulations in teaching [11]. Some instruments such as the four-dimensional framework [8] and Guidelines for developing Content for school and Diksha (ver. 3.0) [14] address the needs of the teachers but they are in the form of binary checklists. Frameworks such as ‘game object mode II’ [9] and Pre-MEGa Framework [12] are detailed but may need significant interpretation by teachers. Also most of the frameworks do not include subject specific and grade specific criteria thereby failing to capture recommended age-specific pedagogies which are related to learning outcomes. We need a framework that addresses teachers’ needs and context, and also incorporates criteria to accommodate the features of available GBL solutions.

III. TULNA GAME-BASED LEARNING INDEX

A. Background: The EdTech Tulna initiative

India has seen an increased market for EdTech products, which has been further fueled by the pandemic [15]. Yet making informed decisions about adoption is challenging for various stakeholders such as schools, teachers, parents, and governments due to inadequate quality standards and lack of unbiased reliable product evaluations. The EdTech Tulna initiative was conceived to address these challenges, and is a research-practice partnership between academic researchers and an NGO, with inputs from teachers and state education departments [16].

EdTech Tulna consists of a set of research-based frameworks to set quality standards for different educational technology usecases such as personalized and adaptive learning, digital classrooms, game-based learning etc, and specific to subjects such as mathematics, language and science. Different views of the frameworks cater to different stakeholder needs. Corresponding to these frameworks are evaluation indexes. These are informed by: i) research on learning theories, multimedia learning, human-computer interaction, and disciplinary teaching practices, ii) recommendations by educational policies in India, and iii) insights gained from various stakeholders and product landscape in the Indian Edtech ecosystem.

B. Design of Tulna game-based learning index

The Tulna GBL index in this study was designed to be used by maths teachers who need a systematic method to identify good quality GBL solutions for their context. The index consists of criteria categorized under three dimensions: Content quality, Pedagogical alignment and Technology & Design, to capture a holistic view of the quality of the design of the GBL solution. The focus of the index is on learning via educational games and includes criteria such as learner autonomy, situating game activities in appropriate context, motivational features, and providing adequate multi-modal, constructive feedback in the game activities, opportunities for collaboration, competition and team-based play to achieve learning goals. In addition, broader criteria related to the three dimensions such as accuracy of content, comprehensibility of language, alignment to national standards, addressing learning gaps, guidance to teachers to integrate the GBL solution, interface design, learner navigation & pace, and universal design.

Each criterion contains guidelines and indicators for reviewers on how to evaluate the GBL solution. The guidelines also include examples to assist teachers in differentiating between solutions of varying quality. Fig. 1 provides an overview of the guideline by showcasing one criterion from one of the constructs: learner agency under Pedagogical Alignment. Evaluation is on a 3-point scale. When all the indicators are met, a GBL solution is considered to *fully incorporate* the criteria. If some indicators are met or found inconsistent in the product, the GBL solution is deemed to *partially incorporate* the criteria. Finally, if very few or none of the indicators are met, the GBL solution is classified as *not-incorporating* the criteria.

Pedagogical Alignment				
	Not at all or minimally incorporated (Tick or leave it blank)	Partially incorporated (Tick or leave it blank)	Completely incorporated (Tick or leave it blank)	Rationale for the score
Learner agency Q. Does the product provide adequate learner autonomy? <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The game allows learners to make various types of choices/decisions to shape their game world. The game allows setting/resetting learners learning goals themselves like choose which mathematics skills they want to practice as game activities The game allows the learner to decide which topic to do and in what sequence. The game allows the learner to choose which challenge levels to attempt The game allows the learner the feeling of being part of the game world. 				

Fig. 1. Criterion of Learner agency in Tulna GBL index

C. Design of training session

The training was designed as a 1.5hr interactive session to explain the criteria in the Tulna GBL index. Evaluation

guidelines were explained using examples from available GBL solutions. The session included multiple activities to encourage active participation from the attendees (see Fig 2 for an example).

Fig. 2. Example of activity in training session

IV. METHOD

The study investigated the perceptions of usefulness, usability, and relevance of the Tulna GBL index among in-service mathematics teachers. The study used a mixed methods approach [17]. Data were collected and analyzed from a pre-survey before the training, and a post-survey and interview after the training session to answer these research questions: Do teachers find the Tulna GBL guidelines useful and usable to identify quality EdTech GBL solutions? How can the teachers adopt it for their use?

A. Participants

We advertised the Edtech Tulna GBL training session, emphasizing its benefits in identifying quality mathematics GBL solutions on social media platforms. Participants included teachers from government, government-aided and private schools from urban and semi-urban areas of India. While the teachers had varying levels of teaching experience, they all had some familiarity with using games.

B. Training session

The teachers who registered were invited to the online training session. During the training session, the criteria in Tulna GBL index were explained using examples from GBL products available to the public. Activities to engage participants were included, such as participants had to choose a good quality product among the two Edtech game solutions presented to them based on the discussed criteria.

C. Data collection and analysis

Participants were requested to complete a pre-survey along with their registration. A total of 141 teachers registered by filling out the pre-survey form. The pre-survey questionnaire consisted of 8 questions aimed at gathering information about the teachers' backgrounds and their perceptions regarding the use of GBL in the classroom.

Out of 141 registered participants, 45 attended the training session. Post the training all 45 teachers were requested to fill a detailed post-training session survey form with the aim of understanding the usefulness and usability of Tulna's GBL index. Additionally, we conducted semi-structured interviews with 15 interested teachers for 20 to 30 minutes in online mode. The researchers prepared a set of 8 questions to guide the interviews, and they also encouraged participants to elaborate on their responses as needed. Some of the interview questions included, "Did your perception of

the quality of GBL solutions change after attending the training session?" and "In what ways does the Tulna GBL index help you address the challenges you encounter when selecting game-based learning solutions?" The audio in the recorded interviews was transcribed, and content analysis [18] was followed to analyze interview responses.

To assess the perceived usability of the Tulna GBL index, we administered the System Usability Scale (SUS) to the teachers after the training session. The SUS is a widely recognized and versatile tool that can be utilized for evaluating the usability of various products [19]. The survey consists of 10 items, and participants are asked to rate their agreement on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The survey includes both positive and negative statements, such as "I thought the Tulna GBL index were easy to use." and "I think that I will need support in the form of training or a technical person to be able to use the Tulna GBL index."

V. FINDINGS

A. Results from pre-survey

1) Teachers' demographics and background

The majority of the registered participants specialized in teaching mathematics to students in grades 6-8 and 9-10 and had a wide range of teaching experience from 1 to 32 years. Among the participants, 21.4% had prior experience using EdTech GBL solutions, while the remaining teachers relied on gamified quizzes, simulation games, puzzle games, and similar resources. The consensus among the teachers was that integrating EdTech GBL solutions into their teaching had numerous benefits for students.

2) Teachers' perception about the benefit of using GBL

An overwhelming majority of the teachers (68.3%) agreed that using EdTech GBL solutions proved beneficial for their students. One teacher highlighted integrating educational content into games motivated learners to actively participate, remarking, "It has helped me a lot in making mathematics more joyful and understandable for my students." Another teacher pointed out that games fostered a sense of connection among learners, as students became actively involved in finding solutions. They stated, "Some students have Math's phobia, and games create interest in mathematics among students."

3) Teachers' challenges and difficulties in choosing Edtech GBL solutions

Despite their willingness to embrace EdTech GBL solutions, teachers faced various challenges in implementing them. These challenges included issues related to network accessibility, open access, interactivity, time constraints, platform feasibility (such as ease of app installation and use), and the availability of smartphones among students. Additionally, a few teachers mentioned the need for training in using EdTech GBL solutions.

From the feedback received, we find that teachers struggle to find appropriate games that align with their students' context and relevant topics. One teacher mentioned, "Sometimes it's difficult to relate games to a topic, and difficult to identify the age-appropriate game, the focus is diverted from learning to play". Another teacher mentioned "Can't understand which game they have to select for a particular topic and difficulty level". "Choosing the best-suited GBL applications is the most challenging task that I've

ever encountered. I thus look for the Learning Objective and then choose the suitable application but face challenges like time constraints, non-availability of games."

4) Teachers' perception of quality of GBL solutions

One of the questions in the pre-survey was, "According to you, what features contribute to a good quality EdTech GBL solution?". Frequency analysis of the responses that were provided in text form shows that the most frequent (more than 50%) quality indicators that were used were Engaging/interesting and Easy to understand/clarity/clear instructions. A few other important (n>30) quality indicators were age appropriate, relevant/educational goals/, interactive, user-friendly/easy of navigation, visual/graphics. Features such as learner agency and storyline were mentioned infrequently (n<4).

B. Results from post-survey

1) Usefulness of Tulna GBL index

To gain insight into the usefulness of our Tulna GBL index we collected both open-ended responses and also questions to be answered in likert scale was done post training session. When asked if the Tulna GBL index help them in selecting suitable EdTech GBL solutions for their use, 19 teachers strongly agreed, 20 agreed, 2 were neutral, 3 disagreed and 1 strongly disagreed on a 5-pt Likert scale. When asked about "How does the Tulna GBL index help you to overcome challenges in selecting GBL solutions" one of the teachers said that "I think this a robust framework to evaluate any EdTech game-based learning solution. I have gained insight of all domains & subdomains of all three pillars i.e. Content Quality, Pedagogical Alignment, and Technology & Design. This will help me to choose appropriate EdTech games for my students." Further, the teachers were asked, "The following criteria are important for selecting edTech GBL solutions.", to which the teachers responded on a 5-pt Likert scale from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree. The results are summarized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Teachers' perception of relevance of criteria in Tulna GBL index on 5-pt Likert Scale (N=45)

We observed a change in the teachers' perception regarding the quality of Edtech GBL solutions. 19 teachers agreed that their ideas about the quality of EdTech GBL solution change in any way after the training session. Elaborating on their response, one of the teachers said "Yes, after the training program I have learned many new parameters which were not known to me earlier which we need to select an EdTech product." Another teacher said, "Yes, the dimensions and construct-wise rubric were very appropriate and aligned to TPACK model so I'll remember it easily while selecting and sorting the GBL tools."

2) Usability Tulna GBL index

Teachers found Tulna GBL index usable as per the SUS (N=45) survey. Overall, the SUS score of the Tulna GBL index was found to be 71.83, which corresponds to a “good” usability score. The SUS score can be decomposed into usability and learnability [20]. The Tulna GBL index scored high on usability i.e. 80.90, while it scored low on learnability i.e. 35.55. The two questions that measure learnability are, “I think that I will need support in the form of training or a technical person to be able to use the Tulna GBL index” and “I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with the Edtech Tulna GBL index.” the low scores on these two items emphasize the requirement of training for teachers

VI. CONCLUSION

Research has shown that teachers' perception of the impact of games in the classroom is closely linked to their actual utilization of games [21]. The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic has compelled teachers across the world to embrace EdTech game-based learning solutions as part of their instructional practices. However, the lack of proper guidance and support has made the selection of high-quality EdTech games a challenging task for teachers. This paper reports the design of Tulna GBL index, a research-based and context-specific tool, which is used to assist teachers in selecting effective EdTech game-based learning solutions for their classrooms. The study conducted with in-service mathematics teachers explores the effect of a training session on teachers' perceptions of EdTech game-based learning solutions, as well as the usefulness and usability of the Tulna GBL index. Our interviews with teachers revealed that they found the Tulna GBL index highly useful, indicating a strong likelihood of its adoption in their teaching practices [22].

There were limitations in our study that should be acknowledged. Firstly, the sampling process relied on teachers who were already interested in using EdTech games, which may have resulted in a biased sample. Therefore, our findings may not fully capture the changes in perception among teachers who are not inclined to use EdTech games. Additionally, the majority of the participating teachers were from urban and semi-urban schools, limiting the generalizability of our results to rural areas. Despite these limitations, our development of the Tulna GBL index specific to mathematics, along with the training session that guides teachers in evaluating game-based learning solutions, contributes towards addressing teachers' needs in selecting quality learning solutions. It also provides a starting point for future research in supporting teachers' adoption of game based EdTech solutions.

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